

Different Types of Magic Rectangles in Construction of Magic Squares of Order 22

The work is also available at the following link:
<https://shorturl.at/qAKT9>

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Abstract

*This work brings magic squares of order 22. These are constructed based on different types of **magic rectangles**. These types are **bordered**, **double digits** and **cornered magic rectangles**. For more details on these types of magic rectangles refer author's work [86]. The construction of magic squares is based on four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 8×14 , 6×16 and 4×18 . In case of **cornered magic rectangles**, three different types are magic squares are studies. Similar kind of work based on **bordered magic rectangles** or **double digits magic squares** can be seen in [67, 84]*

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1 Introduction

This work brings magic squares in very different way. These are based on cornered magic rectangles. First of let's understand what we mean by cornered magic rectangles. There are normal magic rectangles with some extra properties. For examples if remove external border still we left with lower order cornered magic rectangles. Here the external border is understood as one half. See below few examples:

2 Different Type Magic Rectangles

Magic rectangles are well known in the literature. Below is an example of a **magic rectangle** of order 12×20 .

196	109	50	80	79	39	203	61	93	98	18	95	223	85	158	137	108	129	225	224	2410
142	240	154	74	150	73	30	11	120	37	121	46	66	236	218	180	174	166	110	62	2410
115	35	59	232	163	107	133	16	228	49	112	19	209	197	13	113	235	204	149	22	2410
54	24	135	185	117	220	141	145	6	201	202	186	156	51	194	81	119	53	106	34	2410
184	92	168	9	237	29	153	226	207	94	229	1	56	26	7	175	123	84	199	111	2410
12	43	128	136	5	173	138	216	105	78	214	160	144	99	44	114	89	116	231	165	2410
205	212	47	41	146	210	227	86	14	151	71	155	36	181	195	20	126	72	76	139	2410
100	187	217	208	147	177	67	127	27	183	104	77	60	233	191	45	125	42	2	91	2410
215	55	40	58	159	122	161	211	70	176	221	192	148	25	57	96	172	82	48	102	2410
200	206	189	3	198	131	4	33	239	101	21	222	32	178	38	152	65	193	75	130	2410
8	140	171	238	17	31	179	124	170	188	69	63	97	83	213	164	23	143	157	132	2410
15	103	88	182	28	134	10	190	167	90	64	230	219	52	118	169	87	162	68	234	2410
1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446	1446

It is just a simple **magic rectangle**. Below there are three different types of **magic rectangles**:

1. **Bordered Magic Rectangles;**
2. **Double Digits Magic Rectangles;**

3. Cornered Magic Rectangles.

Later these types of magic rectangles are used to construct magic squares. The construction is based on four equal order and equal sums magic rectangles of each type. For details refer author’s work [86, 87, 88, 89]. These are given in following subsections. The examples considered in this work are calculated using softwares by H. White [1].

2.1 Bordered Magic Rectangles

Bordered magic rectangles are very much similar to **bordered magic squares**. The difference is that in case **bordered magic rectangles**, the width and height are different, while in case of **bordered magic squares** the width and height are the same. Below are few examples of **bordered magic rectangles**.

Let’s consider a **bordered magic rectangle** of order 12×18 formed by 216 sequential entries, i.e., from 1 to 216:

8	210	198	5	202	207	21	26	204	194	197	28	1	25	200	9	206	12	1953
201	44	184	35	50	185	30	180	51	172	175	41	177	39	170	165	38	16	1953
215	49	56	66	148	158	57	149	147	157	163	65	55	67	159	72	168	2	1953
22	169	61	88	81	73	141	132	83	131	82	143	78	133	137	156	48	195	1953
14	34	155	140	90	97	95	128	118	96	94	126	124	117	77	62	183	203	1953
4	181	63	130	119	109	105	116	106	103	115	104	110	98	87	154	36	213	1953
24	43	153	75	125	108	112	101	111	114	102	113	107	92	142	64	174	193	1953
190	186	164	138	100	120	122	89	99	121	123	91	93	127	79	53	31	27	1953
6	29	71	80	136	144	76	85	134	86	135	74	139	84	129	146	188	211	1953
199	171	145	151	69	59	160	68	70	60	54	152	162	150	58	161	46	18	1953
214	179	33	182	167	32	187	37	166	45	42	176	40	178	47	52	173	3	1953
205	7	19	212	15	10	196	191	13	23	20	189	216	192	17	208	11	209	1953
1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302	1302

2.2 Double Digits Magic Rectangles

Below we shall give two examples of **double digits magic rectangles**.

Let's consider a **double digits magic rectangle** of order 14×20 formed by 280 sequential entries, i.e., from 1 to 280:

20	273	224	277	28	245	271	58	50	15	59	19	34	13	232	23	221	256	259	233	2810
8	261	57	4	253	36	10	223	231	266	222	262	247	268	49	258	60	25	48	22	2810
226	55	70	189	69	102	193	79	63	94	204	215	214	81	191	93	178	213	249	32	2810
237	44	92	211	212	179	88	202	218	187	77	66	67	200	90	188	68	103	251	30	2810
228	53	192	89	169	110	173	168	158	154	107	119	159	106	149	114	185	96	6	275	2810
252	29	201	80	171	112	108	113	123	127	174	162	122	175	167	132	84	197	243	38	2810
227	54	196	85	150	131	146	137	143	136	147	133	142	140	109	172	91	190	257	24	2810
26	255	186	95	117	164	135	144	138	145	134	148	139	141	156	125	194	87	2	279	2810
244	37	74	207	116	161	176	128	166	124	121	126	129	118	151	170	180	101	7	274	2810
229	52	209	72	120	165	105	153	115	157	160	155	152	163	111	130	64	217	27	254	2810
250	31	99	195	198	78	210	76	75	100	199	61	208	183	62	216	184	104	39	242	2810
16	265	86	182	83	203	71	205	206	181	82	220	73	98	219	65	177	97	269	12	2810
1	278	9	264	235	14	51	43	56	241	248	42	236	41	246	276	21	11	263	234	2810
3	280	272	17	46	267	230	238	225	40	33	239	45	240	35	5	260	270	47	18	2810
1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	

By double digits we understand that, except corners, all others rows or columns taken in pairs are of equal sums. Actually, these are **double digits bordered magic rectangles**, but for simplicity, we shall call it **double digits magic rectangles**. See below sums according to colors:

• Horizontal Sums in Pairs

224	277	28	245	271	58	50	15	59	19	34	13	232	23	221	256
57	4	253	36	10	223	231	266	222	262	247	268	49	258	60	25
281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281
9	264	235	14	51	43	56	241	248	42	236	41	246	276	21	11
272	17	46	267	230	238	225	40	33	239	45	240	35	5	260	270
281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281
69	102	193	79	63	94	204	215	214	81	191	93				
212	179	88	202	218	187	77	66	67	200	90	188				
281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281
198	78	210	76	75	100	199	61	208	183	62	216				
83	203	71	205	206	181	82	220	73	98	219	65				
281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281
173	168	158	154	107	119	159	106								
108	113	123	127	174	162	122	175								
281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281
176	128	166	124	121	126	129	118								
105	153	115	157	160	155	152	163								
281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281
146	137	143	136	147	133	142	140								
135	144	138	145	134	148	139	141								
281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281

• **Vertical Sums in Pairs**

226	55	281	249	32	281	192	89	281	185	96	281
237	44	281	251	30	281	201	80	281	84	197	281
228	53	281	6	275	281	196	85	281	91	190	281
252	29	281	243	38	281	186	95	281	194	87	281
227	54	281	257	24	281	74	207	281	180	101	281
26	255	281	2	279	281	209	72	281	64	217	281
244	37	281	7	274	281						
229	52	281	27	254	281	150	131	281	109	172	281
250	31	281	39	242	281	117	164	281	156	125	281
16	265	281	269	12	281						

More detail on **double digits magic rectangles** refer [86]. There are many magic squares are constructed based on this idea. See the author’s work [67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 72]. Magic squares of orders 7 to 108 can be seen in [81].

2.3 Cornered Magic Rectangle

Let’s consider a **cornered magic rectangle** of order 10×24 formed by 240 sequential entries, i.e., from 1 to 240:

115	113	135	124	136	116	110	111	109	133	129	119	123	107	127	121	98	143	167	74	206	35	8	233	2892
126	128	106	117	105	125	131	130	132	108	112	122	118	134	114	120	90	151	77	164	36	205	229	12	2892
141	96	92	139	154	101	144	99	91	103	88	137	156	86	152	147	148	95	76	165	57	184	213	28	2892
100	145	149	102	87	140	97	142	150	138	153	104	85	155	89	94	146	93	174	67	198	43	27	214	2892
173	177	175	73	83	180	62	63	71	84	171	163	166	161	72	162	159	65	69	81	202	39	209	32	2892
68	64	66	168	158	61	179	178	170	157	70	78	75	80	169	79	82	176	160	172	34	207	240	1	2892
48	197	182	188	55	190	196	54	40	58	46	56	200	191	181	33	38	52	49	199	194	204	224	17	2892
193	44	59	53	186	51	45	187	201	183	195	185	41	50	60	208	203	189	192	42	37	47	25	216	2892
13	5	239	231	6	237	20	220	26	30	227	11	15	219	16	238	31	217	223	9	212	222	7	218	2892
228	236	2	10	235	4	221	21	215	211	14	230	226	22	225	3	210	24	18	232	29	19	23	234	2892
1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	1205	

In this case the distribution is $D_{10 \times 24} := \{1, 2, \dots, 240\}$. Except the corners, the numbers are of equal sums in pairs. Distributions in colors as follows:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
209	210	211	212	213	214	215	216	217	218	219	220	221	222	223	224	225	226	227	228	229	230	231	232	233	234	235	236	237	238	239	240
33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60				
181	182	183	184	185	186	187	188	189	190	191	192	193	194	195	196	197	198	199	200	201	202	203	204	205	206	207	208				
61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84								
157	158	159	160	161	162	163	164	165	166	167	168	169	170	171	172	173	174	175	176	177	178	179	180								
85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	100	101	102	103	104												
137	138	139	140	141	142	143	144	145	146	147	148	149	150	151	152	153	154	155	156												
115	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	114	116	117	118	119	120																
121	122	123	124	125	126	127	128	129	130	131	132	133	134	135	136																

Except the last entries, the others are known by **half-sequential** entries.

More detail on **cornered magic rectangles** refer [86]. Few work on magic squares connected with **cornered magic rectangles** can be seen in [82, 83, 84, 85].

The aim of this work is to write magic squares of order 22 using four equal sums different types of magic rectangles.

3 Magic Squares of Order 22

Initially, let's write two basic magic squares of order 22. These are known by **double digits** and **cornered magic squares** of order 22:

1	Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.com/		https://numbers-magic.com/		@IJTANEJA		22x22		5335											
1	4	483	482	5	479	478	8	9	475	474	12	13	471	470	16	17	467	466	20	24	461	5335
484	481	2	3	480	6	7	477	476	10	11	473	472	14	15	469	468	18	19	465	21	464	5335
61	424	81	83	403	401	400	86	398	88	89	395	91	393	392	94	390	96	97	388	462	23	5335
423	62	404	402	82	84	85	399	87	397	396	90	394	92	93	391	95	389	99	386	463	22	5335
422	63	129	356	145	147	339	337	336	335	151	152	153	331	155	329	157	328	387	98	25	460	5335
64	421	355	130	340	338	146	148	149	150	334	333	332	154	330	156	159	326	385	100	459	26	5335
65	420	131	354	181	304	195	193	291	289	288	198	286	200	201	284	327	158	384	101	458	27	5335
419	66	353	132	303	182	290	292	194	196	197	287	199	285	203	282	325	160	102	383	28	457	5335
418	67	352	133	183	302	217	268	225	259	258	257	226	230	283	202	324	161	382	103	29	456	5335
68	417	134	351	301	184	267	218	254	232	252	233	235	249	281	204	323	162	104	381	455	30	5335
69	416	350	135	300	185	219	266	248	247	239	240	244	237	280	205	163	322	105	380	454	31	5335
415	70	136	349	299	186	265	220	242	238	245	246	241	243	206	279	164	321	379	106	32	453	5335
414	71	137	348	187	298	264	221	231	250	234	251	253	236	278	207	165	320	107	378	33	452	5335
72	413	347	138	188	297	262	223	255	229	227	228	256	260	208	277	319	166	377	108	451	34	5335
73	412	139	346	189	296	224	261	209	275	211	273	216	214	270	272	167	318	376	109	450	35	5335
411	74	345	140	191	294	222	263	276	210	274	212	269	271	215	213	317	168	110	375	36	449	5335
410	75	344	141	295	190	169	315	171	313	312	311	175	176	177	179	307	305	374	111	37	448	5335
76	409	342	143	293	192	316	170	314	172	173	174	310	309	308	306	178	180	112	373	447	38	5335
406	79	144	341	113	371	115	369	368	118	366	120	121	363	123	361	360	358	128	126	446	39	5335
407	78	142	343	372	114	370	116	117	367	119	365	364	122	362	124	125	127	357	359	40	445	5335
77	408	41	443	442	44	45	439	438	48	49	435	434	52	53	431	430	56	426	427	60	57	5335
80	405	444	42	43	441	440	46	47	437	436	50	51	433	432	54	55	429	59	58	425	428	5335
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

2	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				22x22				5335		
241	246	235	248	251	234	211	274	276	209	294	191	325	160	129	356	404	81	59	426	14	471	5335	
236	247	242	245	230	255	216	269	292	193	192	293	331	154	120	365	374	111	429	56	2	483	5335	
250	237	244	239	256	229	272	213	205	280	178	307	148	337	357	128	381	104	70	415	456	29	5335	
243	240	249	238	259	226	220	265	202	283	301	184	162	323	135	350	88	397	419	66	469	16	5335	
225	258	252	232	231	257	264	221	196	289	188	297	333	152	343	142	90	395	409	76	455	30	5335	
260	227	233	253	228	254	271	214	291	194	311	174	334	151	347	138	91	394	43	442	34	451	5335	
261	273	268	223	215	263	219	218	203	282	313	172	159	326	366	119	398	87	432	53	457	28	5335	
224	212	217	262	270	222	267	266	195	290	303	182	340	145	367	118	112	373	73	412	479	6	5335	
200	281	288	199	279	201	275	208	287	207	173	312	158	327	360	125	94	391	51	434	474	11	5335	
285	204	197	286	206	284	210	277	278	198	183	302	156	329	137	348	100	385	431	54	454	31	5335	
175	314	295	300	177	189	186	181	180	306	298	309	315	170	132	353	376	109	72	413	37	448	5335	
310	171	190	185	308	296	299	304	305	179	176	187	146	339	134	351	390	95	52	433	25	460	5335	
319	168	169	330	163	149	164	318	320	157	147	324	335	332	362	123	103	382	441	44	26	459	5335	
166	317	316	155	322	336	321	167	165	328	338	161	153	150	121	364	378	107	422	63	20	465	5335	
370	144	346	344	342	127	368	345	126	122	133	124	136	130	354	369	396	89	74	411	36	449	5335	
115	341	139	141	143	358	117	140	359	363	352	361	349	355	116	131	84	401	418	67	467	18	5335	
102	384	83	92	379	113	388	375	403	399	99	105	389	85	108	98	392	371	428	57	458	27	5335	
383	101	402	393	106	372	97	110	82	86	386	380	96	400	377	387	114	93	436	49	5	480	5335	
425	79	414	48	427	438	408	68	423	410	407	430	61	69	80	50	64	65	45	439	22	463	5335	
60	406	71	437	58	47	77	417	62	75	78	55	424	416	405	435	421	420	46	440	24	461	5335	
3	484	445	464	9	462	15	4	35	473	468	466	33	32	7	13	39	443	447	475	477	41	5335	
482	1	40	21	476	23	470	481	450	12	17	19	452	453	478	472	446	42	38	10	444	8	5335	
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

3.1 Magic Squares of Order 22 with Bordered Magic Rectangles

Below are examples of magic squares of order 22 centered in magic squares of orders 6, 10 and 14 respectively. These are constructed with four equal sums **bordered magic rectangles** of orders 8×14 , 6×16 and 4×18 respectively.

4	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				22x22				5335		
476	478	6	12	2	15	472	465	19	17	467	471	11	484	420	59	72	425	64	424	419	57	5335	
3	29	450	30	458	26	22	34	33	464	457	453	454	482	422	85	406	393	404	80	87	63	5335	
16	462	45	38	448	443	442	41	46	445	39	438	23	469	62	394	101	385	381	103	91	423	5335	
481	449	441	431	50	429	434	52	436	55	53	44	36	4	68	86	94	375	110	391	399	417	5335	
8	460	437	54	435	56	51	433	49	430	432	48	25	477	58	402	392	380	105	93	83	427	5335	
480	24	47	447	37	42	43	444	439	40	446	440	461	5	71	82	387	373	112	98	403	414	5335	
475	31	35	455	27	459	463	451	452	21	28	32	456	10	416	408	389	111	374	96	77	69	5335	
1	7	479	473	483	470	13	20	466	468	18	14	474	9	409	90	97	108	377	388	395	76	5335	
308	171	184	313	176	312	307	169	230	254	227	260	228	256	75	89	102	378	107	383	396	410	5335	
310	197	294	281	292	192	199	175	259	241	246	235	248	226	73	78	386	106	379	99	407	412	5335	
174	282	213	273	269	215	203	311	253	236	247	242	245	232	411	401	95	109	376	390	84	74	5335	
180	198	206	263	222	279	287	305	251	250	237	244	239	234	415	397	382	100	104	384	88	70	5335	
170	290	280	266	219	205	195	315	233	243	240	249	238	252	67	398	79	92	81	405	400	418	5335	
183	194	214	261	224	271	291	302	229	231	258	225	257	255	428	426	413	60	421	61	66	65	5335	
304	202	277	223	262	208	283	181	364	366	118	124	114	127	360	353	131	129	355	359	123	372	5335	
297	296	209	221	264	276	189	188	115	141	338	142	346	138	352	146	145	134	345	341	342	370	5335	
187	201	275	268	217	210	284	298	128	350	157	150	336	331	333	153	158	330	151	326	135	357	5335	
185	190	274	218	267	211	295	300	369	337	329	319	322	317	167	164	324	162	165	156	148	116	5335	
299	289	207	220	265	278	196	186	120	348	325	166	163	168	318	321	161	323	320	160	137	365	5335	
303	285	270	212	216	272	200	182	368	136	159	335	149	154	152	332	327	155	334	328	349	117	5335	
179	286	191	204	193	293	288	306	363	143	147	343	139	347	133	339	340	351	140	144	344	122	5335	
316	314	301	172	309	173	178	177	113	119	367	361	371	358	125	132	354	356	130	126	362	121	5335	
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

30	Inder J. Taneja					https://inderjtaneja.com/					https://numbers-magic.com/					@IJTANEJA					22x22	5335	
482	14	476	15	473	8	10	481	18	7	465	17	5	469	474	466	418	435	61	436	54	51	5335	
2	28	450	26	36	452	32	462	460	22	456	21	34	461	455	483	62	76	406	410	78	423	5335	
472	454	48	37	444	45	441	439	40	438	42	447	446	43	31	13	428	402	96	389	83	57	5335	
1	458	437	448	41	440	44	46	445	47	443	38	39	442	27	484	63	74	85	400	411	422	5335	
479	30	35	459	449	33	453	23	25	463	29	464	451	24	457	6	56	404	93	392	81	429	5335	
19	471	9	470	12	477	475	4	467	478	20	468	480	16	11	3	417	408	90	395	77	68	5335	
338	146	328	145	335	163	283	276	278	290	210	208	206	196	194	284	58	80	393	92	405	427	5335	
158	172	310	314	174	327	205	218	212	272	274	261	223	263	217	280	433	414	391	94	71	52	5335	
332	306	192	293	179	153	203	215	256	254	227	260	228	230	270	282	66	412	88	397	73	419	5335	
159	170	186	299	315	326	199	216	226	241	246	235	248	259	269	286	55	70	390	95	415	430	5335	
329	180	300	185	305	156	193	221	232	236	247	242	245	253	264	292	425	84	396	89	401	60	5335	
152	308	189	296	177	333	281	271	234	250	237	244	239	251	214	204	65	69	399	86	416	420	5335	
154	176	297	188	309	331	285	266	252	243	240	249	238	233	219	200	53	82	398	87	403	432	5335	
337	318	295	190	167	148	287	265	255	231	258	225	257	229	220	198	421	413	91	394	72	64	5335	
162	316	184	301	169	323	288	268	273	213	211	224	262	222	267	197	426	407	79	75	409	59	5335	
151	166	294	191	319	334	201	209	207	195	275	277	279	289	291	202	434	50	424	49	431	67	5335	
321	312	181	304	173	164	370	110	101	111	113	104	106	385	369	103	114	377	380	373	378	386	5335	
161	165	302	183	320	324	387	359	130	122	117	356	128	366	360	118	364	132	354	365	124	98	5335	
149	178	303	182	307	336	109	127	350	139	351	141	345	343	133	342	136	348	144	138	358	376	5335	
325	317	187	298	168	160	388	123	135	346	134	344	140	142	352	143	349	137	341	347	362	97	5335	
330	311	175	171	313	155	102	361	355	363	368	129	357	119	125	367	121	353	131	120	126	383	5335	
322	339	157	340	150	147	99	375	384	374	372	381	379	100	116	382	371	108	105	112	107	115	5335	
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

89	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				22x22				5335		
5	3	474	2	484	478	479	472	8	18	16	473	4	471	19	468	476	15	41	56	439	434	5335	
20	27	36	457	450	30	31	461	459	34	456	453	25	452	23	464	22	465	38	58	427	447	5335	
475	458	449	28	35	455	454	24	26	451	29	32	460	33	462	21	463	10	438	72	413	47	5335	
470	482	11	483	1	7	6	13	477	467	469	12	481	14	466	17	9	480	39	421	64	446	5335	
113	128	367	362	151	329	332	146	152	337	154	150	338	336	169	320	310	171	448	414	71	37	5335	
111	135	350	374	340	327	326	160	323	164	157	161	322	145	176	303	182	309	442	66	419	43	5335	
366	144	341	119	330	158	159	325	162	321	328	324	163	155	173	181	304	312	443	67	418	42	5335	
110	349	136	375	149	156	153	339	333	148	331	335	147	334	319	180	305	166	436	425	60	49	5335	
376	342	143	109	211	280	270	209	256	254	227	260	228	230	313	307	178	172	44	423	62	441	5335	
370	138	347	115	269	263	222	216	226	241	246	235	248	259	168	177	308	317	54	70	415	431	5335	
371	139	346	114	272	224	261	213	232	236	247	242	245	253	311	306	179	174	52	420	65	433	5335	
364	353	132	121	210	221	264	275	234	250	237	244	239	251	315	184	301	170	437	417	68	48	5335	
116	351	134	369	212	262	223	273	252	243	240	249	238	233	167	302	183	318	40	61	424	445	5335	
126	142	343	359	277	217	268	208	255	231	258	225	257	229	314	165	175	316	435	416	69	50	5335	
124	348	137	361	206	266	219	279	294	196	193	295	293	188	291	299	187	189	55	59	426	430	5335	
365	345	140	120	214	220	265	271	185	201	204	200	287	197	282	283	286	300	432	428	57	53	5335	
112	130	355	373	278	267	218	207	195	284	281	285	198	288	203	202	199	290	440	63	422	45	5335	
363	344	141	122	276	205	215	274	296	289	292	190	192	297	194	186	298	191	51	429	46	444	5335	
127	356	129	358	77	75	402	74	412	406	407	400	80	90	88	401	76	399	91	396	404	87	5335	
360	131	354	125	92	99	108	385	378	95	103	389	387	106	384	381	97	380	392	94	102	393	5335	
368	133	352	117	403	386	377	100	107	390	382	96	98	379	101	104	388	105	93	391	383	82	5335	
123	357	118	372	398	410	83	411	73	79	78	85	405	395	397	84	409	86	394	89	81	408	5335	
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

More examples of similar kind are given in pdf file in author’s site <https://shorturl.at/qAKT9>.

3.2 Magic Squares of Order 22 with Double Digits Magic Rectangles

Below are examples of magic squares of order 22 centered in magic squares of order 6 and 10 respectively. These are constructed with four equal sums **double digits magic rectangles** of orders 8×14 and 6×16 respectively.

7	Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA			22x22		5335							
29	454	450	30	458	26	22	34	33	464	457	453	3	482	85	87	406	393	404	80	422	63	5335	
31	456	35	455	27	459	463	451	452	21	28	32	16	469	398	400	79	92	81	405	62	423	5335	
462	23	45	38	448	41	442	443	46	445	39	438	481	4	394	91	101	385	381	103	68	417	5335	
449	36	441	50	52	431	434	429	436	55	53	44	8	477	86	399	94	375	110	391	58	427	5335	
460	25	437	435	433	54	51	56	49	430	432	48	480	5	402	83	392	380	105	93	71	414	5335	
24	461	47	447	37	444	43	42	439	40	446	440	475	10	90	395	387	373	112	98	416	69	5335	
478	6	12	2	15	467	472	465	17	19	471	11	476	484	78	407	389	111	374	96	409	76	5335	
7	479	473	483	470	18	13	20	468	466	14	474	1	9	408	77	97	108	377	388	75	410	5335	
197	199	294	281	292	192	310	175	225	259	258	257	226	230	89	396	102	378	107	383	73	412	5335	
286	288	191	204	193	293	174	311	254	232	252	233	235	249	82	403	386	106	379	99	411	74	5335	
282	203	213	273	269	215	180	305	248	247	239	240	244	237	401	84	95	109	376	390	415	70	5335	
198	287	206	263	222	279	170	315	242	238	245	246	241	243	397	88	382	100	104	384	67	418	5335	
290	195	280	266	219	205	183	302	231	250	234	251	253	236	59	72	425	64	424	419	420	57	5335	
194	291	214	261	224	271	187	298	255	229	227	228	256	260	426	413	60	421	61	66	428	65	5335	
202	283	277	220	265	208	297	188	141	342	338	142	346	352	138	146	145	134	345	341	115	370	5335	
296	189	209	221	264	276	304	181	143	344	147	343	139	133	347	339	340	351	140	144	128	357	5335	
201	284	275	268	217	210	185	300	350	135	157	150	336	331	333	153	158	330	151	326	369	116	5335	
190	295	274	218	267	211	299	186	337	148	329	319	322	317	167	165	324	162	164	156	120	365	5335	
289	196	207	223	262	278	303	182	348	137	325	166	163	168	318	320	161	323	321	160	368	117	5335	
285	200	270	212	216	272	179	306	136	349	159	335	149	154	152	332	327	155	334	328	363	122	5335	
171	184	313	176	312	307	308	169	366	118	124	114	127	360	353	131	129	355	359	123	364	372	5335	
314	301	172	309	173	178	316	177	119	367	361	371	358	125	132	354	356	130	126	362	113	121	5335	
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

37	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				22x22				5335		
28	455	450	26	36	452	32	462	460	22	456	21	34	461	2	483	76	78	406	410	62	423	5335	
30	457	35	459	449	33	453	23	25	463	29	464	451	24	472	13	407	409	79	75	428	57	5335	
454	31	48	40	444	45	441	439	37	438	42	447	446	43	1	484	404	81	390	95	63	422	5335	
458	27	437	445	41	440	44	46	448	47	443	38	39	442	479	6	74	411	93	392	56	429	5335	
14	476	15	473	5	17	481	18	7	465	10	8	469	474	482	466	402	83	85	400	417	68	5335	
471	9	470	12	480	468	4	467	478	20	475	477	16	11	19	3	414	71	90	395	58	427	5335	
172	174	310	314	158	327	195	193	291	289	288	198	286	200	201	284	80	405	393	92	433	52	5335	
311	313	175	171	332	153	290	292	194	196	197	287	199	285	203	282	408	77	391	94	66	419	5335	
306	179	187	298	159	326	217	268	225	259	258	257	226	230	283	202	412	73	88	397	55	430	5335	
170	315	186	299	329	156	267	218	254	232	252	233	235	249	281	204	70	415	398	87	425	60	5335	
180	305	300	185	152	333	219	266	248	247	239	240	244	237	280	205	84	401	396	89	65	420	5335	
308	177	189	296	154	331	265	220	242	238	245	246	241	243	206	279	69	416	399	86	53	432	5335	
176	309	297	188	337	148	264	221	231	250	234	251	253	236	278	207	82	403	96	389	421	64	5335	
318	167	303	182	149	336	262	223	255	229	227	228	256	260	208	277	413	72	91	394	426	59	5335	
316	169	184	301	151	334	224	261	209	275	211	273	216	214	270	272	435	61	436	54	418	51	5335	
166	319	294	191	162	323	222	263	276	210	274	212	269	271	215	213	50	424	49	431	434	67	5335	
312	173	181	304	321	164	359	124	130	122	117	356	128	366	360	118	354	132	364	365	387	98	5335	
165	320	302	183	161	324	361	126	355	363	368	129	357	119	125	367	131	353	121	120	109	376	5335	
178	307	295	190	325	160	127	358	350	139	342	141	345	343	144	138	136	348	133	351	388	97	5335	
317	168	192	293	330	155	123	362	135	346	143	344	140	142	341	347	349	137	352	134	102	383	5335	
146	328	145	335	338	163	110	101	111	113	104	106	385	369	103	114	377	380	373	378	370	386	5335	
339	157	340	150	322	147	375	384	374	372	381	379	100	116	382	371	108	105	112	107	99	115	5335	
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

In this case, we don't have **double digits magic rectangles** of order 4×18 . More examples of similar kind are given in **pdf file** in author's site <https://shorturl.at/qAKT9>.

3.3 Magic Squares of Order 22 with Cornered Magic Rectangles

We have written in three different styles magic squares of order 22 using 4 equal sums **cornered magic rectangles**. These are centered in magic squares of order 6, 10 and 14.

3.3.1 First Type

Below are examples of magic squares of order 22 centered in magic squares of order 6, 10 and 14 respectively. These are constructed with four equal sums **cornered magic rectangles** of orders 8×14 , 6×16 and 4×18 respectively.

14	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				22x22				5335		
429	52	435	54	51	430	53	436	437	48	21	464	4	481	424	61	399	86	101	384	379	106	5335	
56	433	50	431	434	55	432	49	44	441	461	24	12	473	59	426	83	402	391	94	378	107	5335	
439	447	445	39	47	37	442	443	45	41	34	451	468	17	427	58	84	401	392	93	105	380	5335	
46	38	40	446	438	448	43	42	444	440	27	458	484	1	414	71	91	394	385	100	373	112	5335	
450	22	449	32	28	29	455	462	459	31	460	33	5	480	70	415	397	88	102	383	376	109	5335	
35	463	36	453	457	456	30	23	26	454	452	25	470	15	420	65	79	406	382	103	110	375	5335	
471	16	19	13	483	478	10	3	6	467	11	476	477	465	57	428	407	78	95	390	111	374	5335	
14	469	466	472	2	7	475	482	479	18	474	9	20	8	412	73	92	393	381	104	108	377	5335	
310	177	309	169	304	172	312	187	241	246	235	248	253	232	76	409	77	408	99	388	96	387	5335	
175	308	176	316	181	313	298	173	236	247	242	245	251	234	68	417	403	82	97	386	389	98	5335	
196	282	192	290	291	204	188	297	250	237	244	239	259	226	422	63	398	85	405	81	396	90	5335	
289	203	293	195	281	194	179	306	243	240	249	238	233	252	410	75	400	87	80	404	89	395	5335	
270	207	280	213	202	283	303	182	228	227	260	254	230	256	64	413	62	416	425	74	419	67	5335	
215	278	272	205	189	296	178	307	257	258	225	231	229	255	72	421	423	69	60	411	66	418	5335	
224	261	206	279	200	285	302	183	124	130	113	118	368	354	123	356	360	370	127	366	121	365	5335	
219	266	211	274	284	201	314	171	355	361	372	367	117	131	362	129	125	115	358	119	364	120	5335	
222	263	277	208	193	292	301	184	363	122	343	140	337	141	144	147	138	350	139	340	352	339	5335	
267	218	209	276	197	288	170	315	126	359	345	142	148	344	341	338	347	135	346	145	133	146	5335	
265	220	271	214	294	191	185	300	357	128	136	349	156	152	328	155	159	334	149	335	332	325	5335	
262	223	273	212	286	199	305	180	132	353	137	348	333	329	157	330	326	151	336	150	153	160	5335	
264	221	216	269	198	287	174	311	114	371	143	342	327	158	319	318	168	164	322	161	165	323	5335	
217	268	210	275	295	190	186	299	369	116	351	134	154	331	166	167	317	321	163	324	320	162	5335	
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

49	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				22x22				5335		
44	448	39	437	443	46	45	442	438	41	447	40	29	456	1	484	417	68	77	408	95	390	5335	
441	37	446	48	42	439	440	43	47	444	38	445	450	35	470	15	52	433	412	73	399	86	5335	
464	26	449	34	460	453	462	24	457	22	30	454	33	27	19	466	435	50	411	74	93	392	5335	
21	459	36	451	25	32	23	461	28	463	455	31	458	452	482	3	64	421	403	82	89	396	5335	
12	13	467	480	2	474	481	471	465	17	10	7	16	9	477	479	434	51	81	404	87	398	5335	
473	472	18	5	483	11	4	14	20	468	475	478	469	476	6	8	436	49	78	407	391	94	5335	
152	150	160	331	339	323	241	246	235	248	253	232	223	262	210	275	67	418	401	84	393	92	5335	
333	335	325	154	162	146	236	247	242	245	233	252	211	274	197	288	420	65	80	405	88	397	5335	
169	177	310	314	156	329	250	237	244	239	251	234	264	221	286	199	58	427	69	416	91	394	5335	
316	308	171	175	148	337	243	240	249	238	259	226	219	266	291	194	55	430	414	71	389	96	5335	
187	298	166	319	147	338	228	227	254	260	230	256	217	268	287	198	53	432	83	402	400	85	5335	
300	185	168	317	330	155	257	258	231	225	229	255	263	222	202	283	60	425	70	415	395	90	5335	
294	191	315	170	327	158	220	218	272	261	216	271	270	212	280	205	428	57	410	79	72	409	5335	
182	303	178	307	157	328	265	267	213	224	269	214	273	215	200	285	59	426	406	75	413	76	5335	
181	304	320	165	159	326	207	276	204	282	201	290	289	277	193	206	423	66	61	422	54	429	5335	
301	184	305	180	332	153	278	209	281	203	284	195	196	208	279	292	419	62	424	63	431	56	5335	
299	186	318	167	334	151	105	111	378	102	376	384	112	98	372	369	386	115	382	97	108	385	5335	
192	293	179	306	145	340	374	380	107	383	109	101	373	387	113	116	99	370	103	388	377	100	5335	
302	183	311	174	336	149	106	379	123	360	367	359	354	364	129	122	119	361	117	132	358	130	5335	
189	296	309	176	321	164	381	104	125	362	118	126	131	121	356	363	366	124	368	353	127	355	5335	
295	190	172	313	163	322	375	110	357	128	343	134	347	144	352	350	141	139	345	136	342	137	5335	
188	297	173	312	324	161	114	371	365	120	142	351	138	341	133	135	344	346	140	349	143	348	5335	
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

110	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA		22x22		5335						
457	36	27	450	30	31	461	459	34	456	453	25	452	23	464	22	20	465	38	447	58	427	5335	
28	449	458	35	455	454	24	26	451	29	32	460	33	462	21	463	475	10	438	47	67	418	5335	
2	474	3	484	478	479	472	8	18	16	473	4	471	19	468	476	5	15	448	37	421	64	5335	
483	11	482	1	7	6	13	477	467	469	12	481	14	466	17	9	470	480	436	49	414	71	5335	
128	367	113	362	325	159	158	328	161	322	164	323	153	332	172	313	177	308	442	43	66	419	5335	
357	118	123	372	160	326	327	157	324	163	321	162	336	149	171	314	184	301	443	42	72	413	5335	
135	350	111	374	338	151	156	145	330	339	148	152	331	335	309	176	303	182	39	446	425	60	5335	
342	143	366	119	147	334	329	340	155	146	337	333	150	154	318	167	306	179	44	441	423	62	5335	
349	136	110	375	277	210	213	270	225	259	258	257	226	230	165	320	183	302	54	431	70	415	5335	
131	354	376	109	208	275	215	272	254	232	252	233	235	249	319	166	305	180	52	433	420	65	5335	
138	347	370	115	268	217	273	212	248	247	239	240	244	237	317	168	304	181	437	48	417	68	5335	
139	346	371	114	263	222	269	216	242	238	245	246	241	243	310	175	178	307	40	445	61	424	5335	
353	132	364	121	218	267	274	211	231	250	234	251	253	236	170	311	173	316	435	50	416	69	5335	
351	134	116	369	261	224	205	280	255	229	227	228	256	260	174	315	312	169	55	430	59	426	5335	
133	352	360	125	221	264	276	209	194	196	293	292	300	188	191	290	186	295	432	53	428	57	5335	
348	137	124	361	223	262	214	271	289	291	192	193	185	297	294	195	299	190	440	45	63	422	5335	
345	140	365	120	220	265	279	206	298	187	198	288	283	285	201	199	204	282	41	434	56	439	5335	
130	355	112	373	266	219	207	278	189	296	287	197	202	200	284	286	281	203	51	444	429	46	5335	
344	141	126	359	77	87	75	402	91	399	406	412	400	80	90	88	401	76	407	74	396	404	5335	
356	129	127	358	398	408	410	83	394	86	79	73	85	405	395	397	84	409	78	411	89	81	5335	
142	343	363	122	92	393	99	94	385	378	95	103	389	387	106	384	102	97	380	392	108	381	5335	
144	341	368	117	403	82	386	391	100	107	390	382	96	98	379	101	383	388	105	93	377	104	5335	
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

3.3.2 Second Type

Below are examples of magic squares of order 22 centered in magic squares of order 6 and 10 respectively. These are constructed with four equal sums **cornered magic rectangles** of orders 8×14 , and 6×16 respectively.

16	Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.com/		https://numbers-magic.com/		@IJTANEJA		22x22		5335											
1	484	28	457	438	47	56	51	54	435	433	430	432	49	68	411	419	70	413	76	58	425	5335
478	7	450	35	39	446	429	434	431	50	52	55	53	436	74	417	66	415	72	409	427	60	5335
477	8	24	461	448	440	38	43	445	41	439	441	48	42	67	418	399	401	80	87	81	407	5335
9	476	458	27	45	37	447	442	40	444	46	44	437	443	62	423	84	86	405	398	404	78	5335
472	13	459	449	21	34	32	452	29	25	462	454	30	463	424	61	393	92	100	389	383	98	5335
4	481	36	26	464	451	453	33	456	460	23	31	455	22	410	75	88	397	96	385	102	387	5335
480	466	20	11	471	6	470	10	469	2	17	473	482	18	57	428	85	400	384	101	375	110	5335
19	5	465	474	14	479	15	475	16	483	468	12	3	467	421	64	91	394	99	386	374	111	5335
261	224	271	214	282	203	303	182	230	254	227	260	228	256	416	69	82	403	103	382	112	373	5335
220	265	279	206	190	295	184	301	259	241	246	235	248	226	426	59	406	79	390	95	108	377	5335
267	218	277	208	281	204	171	314	253	236	247	242	245	232	71	414	83	402	388	97	378	107	5335
222	263	207	278	200	285	181	304	251	250	237	244	239	234	422	63	396	89	391	94	105	380	5335
219	266	215	270	196	289	315	170	233	243	240	249	238	252	65	420	408	77	93	392	109	376	5335
262	223	205	280	197	288	178	307	229	231	258	225	257	255	412	73	395	90	381	104	379	106	5335
221	264	274	211	287	198	310	175	368	115	371	113	126	364	358	132	356	124	366	354	120	128	5335
268	217	275	210	294	191	187	298	117	370	114	372	359	121	127	353	129	361	119	131	357	365	5335
269	212	213	276	291	194	174	311	343	135	140	147	341	139	351	148	133	347	342	344	118	367	5335
216	273	209	272	199	286	299	186	142	350	345	338	144	346	134	337	352	138	141	143	360	125	5335
189	202	293	195	292	284	179	306	157	335	336	329	158	326	151	325	155	153	349	136	369	116	5335
296	283	192	290	201	193	308	177	328	150	149	156	327	159	334	160	332	330	137	348	130	355	5335
300	180	172	316	173	302	309	188	323	322	161	317	320	166	167	164	152	333	340	145	363	122	5335
185	305	313	169	312	183	297	176	162	163	324	168	165	319	318	321	331	154	146	339	123	362	5335
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

66	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				22x22				5335		
8	477	25	460	43	444	438	38	37	445	443	48	446	45	439	44	57	422	58	429	423	66	5335	
6	479	33	452	442	41	47	447	448	40	42	437	39	440	46	441	63	428	427	56	62	419	5335	
16	469	454	27	22	24	459	34	464	455	462	35	449	453	28	29	426	59	75	77	405	413	5335	
475	10	458	31	463	461	26	451	21	30	23	450	36	32	457	456	54	431	408	410	80	72	5335	
483	18	12	4	1	3	474	13	15	476	478	471	480	465	19	468	424	61	415	70	391	94	5335	
467	2	473	481	484	482	11	472	470	9	7	14	5	20	466	17	432	53	407	78	86	399	5335	
188	297	320	165	156	329	195	193	291	289	288	198	286	200	201	284	64	421	402	83	395	90	5335	
304	181	170	315	157	328	290	292	194	196	197	287	199	285	203	282	50	435	412	73	96	389	5335	
183	302	305	180	323	162	217	268	241	246	235	248	253	232	283	202	420	65	81	404	400	85	5335	
293	192	178	307	336	149	267	218	236	247	242	245	251	234	281	204	417	68	74	411	398	87	5335	
299	186	316	169	327	158	219	266	250	237	244	239	259	226	280	205	434	51	71	414	93	392	5335	
190	295	309	176	330	155	265	220	243	240	249	238	233	252	206	279	67	418	409	76	91	394	5335	
189	296	318	167	337	148	264	221	228	227	260	254	230	256	278	207	430	55	69	416	393	92	5335	
298	187	168	317	146	339	262	223	257	258	225	231	229	255	208	277	49	436	84	401	88	397	5335	
294	191	313	172	151	334	224	261	209	275	211	273	216	214	270	272	60	425	406	79	390	95	5335	
185	300	166	319	161	324	222	263	276	210	274	212	269	271	215	213	433	52	82	403	89	396	5335	
303	182	174	311	153	332	369	100	101	112	386	388	115	372	106	103	387	108	380	107	375	371	5335	
184	301	310	175	321	164	116	385	384	373	99	97	370	113	379	382	98	377	105	378	114	110	5335	
173	306	177	314	160	325	125	364	355	353	129	126	363	128	117	366	131	118	362	358	109	376	5335	
312	179	171	308	154	331	360	121	130	132	356	359	122	357	368	119	354	367	127	123	374	111	5335	
145	326	163	338	333	150	143	351	141	137	135	343	345	136	139	341	352	347	120	365	102	383	5335	
340	159	322	147	335	152	342	134	344	348	350	142	140	349	346	144	133	138	361	124	381	104	5335	
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

3.3.3 Third Type

Below are examples of magic squares of order 22 centered in magic squares of order 6, 10 and 14 respectively. These are constructed with four equal sums **cornered magic rectangles** of orders 8×14 , 6×16 and 4×18 respectively.

22	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				22x22		5335				
480	3	483	1	14	476	470	468	20	12	478	466	8	16	373	112	383	102	393	92	415	70	5335	
5	482	2	484	471	9	15	17	465	473	7	19	469	477	108	377	391	94	78	407	72	413	5335	
455	23	28	35	453	27	463	36	21	459	454	456	6	479	379	106	389	96	394	91	75	410	5335	
30	462	457	450	32	458	22	449	464	26	29	31	472	13	110	375	95	390	88	397	69	416	5335	
45	447	448	441	46	438	39	437	43	41	461	24	481	4	107	378	103	382	84	401	427	58	5335	
440	38	37	44	439	47	446	48	444	442	25	460	18	467	374	111	386	99	85	400	66	419	5335	
435	434	49	429	432	54	55	52	40	445	452	33	475	10	109	376	93	392	399	86	422	63	5335	
50	51	436	56	53	431	430	433	443	42	34	451	11	474	380	105	387	98	406	79	59	426	5335	
180	299	307	182	301	188	170	313	241	246	235	248	253	232	381	100	101	388	403	82	62	423	5335	
186	305	178	303	184	297	315	172	236	247	242	245	251	234	104	385	97	384	87	398	411	74	5335	
169	316	287	289	192	193	199	295	250	237	244	239	259	226	77	405	90	83	404	396	67	418	5335	
174	311	196	198	293	292	286	190	243	240	249	238	233	252	408	80	395	402	89	81	420	65	5335	
312	173	281	204	212	277	271	210	228	227	260	254	230	256	60	68	412	428	61	414	421	76	5335	
177	308	197	288	208	273	214	275	257	258	225	231	229	255	425	417	73	57	424	71	409	64	5335	
179	306	200	285	272	213	263	222	366	119	140	345	326	159	168	163	166	323	321	318	320	161	5335	
300	185	203	282	278	207	262	223	121	364	338	147	151	334	317	322	319	162	164	167	165	324	5335	
304	181	194	291	215	270	224	261	365	120	136	349	336	328	150	155	333	153	327	329	160	154	5335	
314	171	294	191	211	274	220	265	113	372	346	139	157	149	335	330	152	332	158	156	325	331	5335	
183	302	195	290	276	209	266	219	360	125	347	337	146	133	144	342	141	137	340	350	142	351	5335	
310	175	284	201	279	206	217	268	116	369	148	138	339	352	341	143	344	348	145	135	343	134	5335	
298	187	296	189	205	280	221	264	368	354	132	123	359	122	358	118	357	130	129	361	114	370	5335	
309	176	283	202	269	216	267	218	131	117	353	362	126	363	127	367	128	355	356	124	371	115	5335	
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

77	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				22x22				5335		
465	4	483	16	482	484	19	468	10	7	5	12	476	11	471	467	92	393	401	84	65	420	5335	
20	481	2	469	3	1	466	17	475	478	480	473	9	474	18	14	400	85	74	411	433	52	5335	
29	460	451	449	33	30	459	32	21	462	35	22	458	454	13	472	87	398	416	69	419	66	5335	
456	25	34	36	452	455	26	453	464	23	450	463	31	27	470	15	395	90	72	413	432	53	5335	
47	447	45	41	39	439	441	40	43	437	448	443	24	461	6	479	389	96	412	73	423	62	5335	
438	38	440	444	446	46	44	445	442	48	37	42	457	28	477	8	94	391	405	80	426	59	5335	
153	326	154	333	327	162	195	193	291	289	288	198	286	200	201	284	93	392	414	71	61	424	5335	
159	332	331	152	158	323	290	292	194	196	197	287	199	285	203	282	394	91	82	403	60	425	5335	
330	155	171	173	309	317	217	268	230	254	227	260	228	256	283	202	390	95	409	76	417	68	5335	
150	335	312	314	176	168	267	218	259	241	246	235	248	226	281	204	89	396	70	415	50	435	5335	
328	157	165	320	187	298	219	266	253	236	247	242	245	232	280	205	399	86	78	407	58	427	5335	
336	149	311	174	189	296	265	220	251	250	237	244	239	234	206	279	88	397	406	79	55	430	5335	
160	325	306	179	299	186	264	221	233	243	240	249	238	252	278	207	77	402	81	410	64	421	5335	
146	339	316	169	192	293	262	223	229	231	258	225	257	255	208	277	408	83	75	404	57	428	5335	
324	161	177	308	295	190	224	261	209	275	211	273	216	214	270	272	49	422	67	434	429	54	5335	
337	148	170	315	302	183	222	263	276	210	274	212	269	271	215	213	436	63	418	51	431	56	5335	
338	147	167	318	182	303	104	381	121	364	139	347	342	134	133	349	348	144	350	141	343	140	5335	
145	340	313	172	304	181	102	383	129	356	346	138	143	351	352	136	137	341	135	344	142	345	5335	
334	151	319	166	297	188	112	373	358	123	118	120	363	130	368	359	366	131	353	357	124	125	5335	
156	329	310	175	184	301	379	106	362	127	367	365	122	355	117	126	119	354	132	128	361	360	5335	
163	322	180	305	294	191	387	114	108	100	99	378	97	111	115	380	382	375	384	369	109	372	5335	
321	164	178	307	185	300	371	98	377	385	386	107	388	374	370	105	103	110	101	116	376	113	5335	
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

129	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				22x22				5335		
474	4	3	484	478	479	472	8	18	16	473	2	471	19	468	476	5	15	58	427	448	37	5335	
11	481	482	1	7	6	13	477	467	469	12	483	14	466	17	9	470	480	67	418	438	47	5335	
457	36	22	464	30	31	461	459	34	456	453	25	452	23	450	27	20	465	421	64	38	447	5335	
28	449	463	21	455	454	24	26	451	29	32	460	33	462	35	458	475	10	414	71	436	49	5335	
113	362	128	367	152	151	339	338	145	329	337	330	150	154	302	183	318	167	66	419	442	43	5335	
123	372	357	118	333	334	146	147	340	156	148	155	331	335	179	306	176	309	72	413	443	42	5335	
111	374	135	350	157	164	323	326	163	325	324	158	153	332	178	307	171	314	425	60	39	446	5335	
366	119	342	143	328	321	162	159	322	160	161	327	336	149	308	177	168	317	423	62	44	441	5335	
110	375	349	136	214	269	278	209	225	259	258	257	226	230	181	304	310	175	70	415	54	431	5335	
376	109	131	354	216	271	207	276	254	232	252	233	235	249	305	180	319	166	420	65	52	433	5335	
370	115	138	347	273	212	218	267	248	247	239	240	244	237	184	301	165	320	417	68	437	48	5335	
371	114	139	346	272	213	262	223	242	238	245	246	241	243	303	182	172	313	61	424	40	445	5335	
364	121	353	132	275	210	263	222	231	250	234	251	253	236	173	316	311	170	416	69	435	50	5335	
116	369	351	134	211	274	265	220	255	229	227	228	256	260	312	169	315	174	59	426	55	430	5335	
360	125	133	352	208	277	219	266	297	188	288	283	200	281	198	203	201	286	428	57	432	53	5335	
124	361	348	137	206	279	221	264	190	295	197	202	285	204	287	282	284	199	63	422	440	45	5335	
365	120	345	140	270	215	224	261	193	195	293	289	294	299	296	185	194	187	56	439	41	434	5335	
112	373	130	355	280	205	268	217	290	292	192	196	191	186	189	300	291	298	429	46	51	444	5335	
126	359	344	141	92	393	99	94	385	378	95	103	389	387	106	384	102	97	380	392	108	381	5335	
127	358	356	129	403	82	386	391	100	107	390	382	96	98	379	101	383	388	105	93	377	104	5335	
363	122	142	343	77	87	75	402	91	399	406	404	400	80	90	88	401	76	407	74	396	412	5335	
368	117	144	341	398	408	410	83	394	86	79	81	85	405	395	397	84	409	78	411	89	73	5335	
5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335	5335

More examples of similar kind are given in pdf file in author's site <https://shorturl.at/qAKT9>.

Acknowledgement

The examples considered in the work are considered using different softwares by H. White [1]. The author is thankful to H. White for providing these softwares.

4 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

References

- [1] **H. White**, Bordered Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/Download.html>
- **Block-Wise Magic Squares**
- [2] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 8 to 108, May 15, 2019, pp. 1-43, **Zenodo**, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2843326>.
- [3] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order $4k$, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-17, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554288>.
- [4] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.
- [5] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders $3k$ and $6k$, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554895>.
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• Bordered Magic Squares

[9] **Inder J. Taneja**, Nested Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sums, Pythagorean Triples, and Borders Differences, **Zenodo**, June 14, 2019, pp. 1-59, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246586>.

[10] **Inder J. Taneja**, Symmetric Properties of Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, June 29, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3262170>.

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